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In Pursuit of the Unattainable: The Conundrum of Artificial General Intelligence

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For it is quite certain that in terms of merely mechanical principles of nature we cannot even adequately become familiar with, much less explain, organized beings and how they are internally possible. So certain is this that we may boldly state that it is absurd for human beings even to attempt it, or to hope that perhaps some day another Newton might arise who would explain to us, in terms of natural laws unordered by any intention, how even a mere blade of grass is produced. Rather, we must absolutely deny that human beings have such insight.

- (Kant 1987, § 75)

0. Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to argue against achieving Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) revolving around (i) programs being insufficient to create human-like intelligence due to their lack of semantic grasping and (ii) our inability to effectively model complex systems. The challenge is magnified by our struggles to mathematically explain basic complex phenomena, raising doubts about our capability to replicate intricate structures like human intelligence or vertebrate brains. Attaining AGI requires transcending the limitations of current mathematical and computational paradigms, with a call for a revolutionary leap in both areas. Despite these challenges, replicating non-human intelligence, even if encountered, remains unfeasible due to complexities beyond our current capabilities. Overall, achieving AGI presents an immensely challenging prospect for the foreseeable future.

1. Introduction

“A misaligned superintelligent AGI could cause grievous harm to the world; an autocratic regime with a decisive superintelligence lead could do that too”¹. – Sam Altman (CEO of OpenAI)

“The development of full artificial intelligence could spell the end of the human race. Once humans develop artificial intelligence, it will take off on its own and redesign itself at an ever-increasing rate. Humans, who are limited by slow biological evolution, couldn’t compete and would be superseded”². - Stephen Hawking

As evidenced by the forementioned quotes, eminent figures exhibit a profound and pervasive apprehension concerning the prospective trajectory and implications of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). Most of these quotes include specific assumptions regarding AGI. The contemporary debate largely focuses on the danger of AGI on human civilization. Will AGI be a threat to humanity? Can we as humans set boundaries and regulations that control AGIs in the future? Will AGI take over the world? How will we as humans survive the so called “singularity”³.

In fact, the mission of OpenAI, the company responsible for the creation of the famous Large Language Model ChatGPT, is “to ensure that artificial general intelligence—AI systems that are generally smarter than humans—benefits all of humanity”⁴. A very large number of movies⁵ and books⁶ in the realm of sci fi and futuristic ideas are all dealing with similar questions.

An increasing number of experts across various fields believe that rapid advancements in

¹ Altman 2023.

² Cellan-Jones 2014.

³ The Singularity is a hypothetical future point in time at which artificial intelligence advances beyond human control, resulting in unforeseeable consequences for human civilization see Eden et al. 2012.

⁴ <https://openai.com/about>

⁵ such as the 2004 movie I, Robot; the 1968 movie 2001: A Space Odyssey, the 2014 movie Ex Machina; the film series Blade Runner; and many many others.

⁶ Such as the novel Neuromancer by William Gibson.

disruptive technologies, such as AI, robotics, genetic engineering, and nanotechnology, might culminate in what's termed the "technological singularity." This anticipated event or period is expected to fundamentally transform human civilization, and possibly the very essence of human nature, likely occurring before the midpoint of the 21st century (Eden et al. 2012, p. 1).

All these hypotheses and questions are remarkably interesting and stimulating, yet they all assume the same thing: that AGI is possible and achievable. Many seem certain that we will achieve AGI even sooner than expected.

But is AGI in fact achievable? The answer, especially after the current trends in AI and the mass adoption of AI powered software might seem obvious. Why not? But have we really contemplated this enough? Could it really be the case that there are major obstacles that stand before our creation of AGI?

The central idea of the thesis is that in fact there do seem to exist obstacles in the way of AGI achievability. The nature of these obstacles can be of diverse types including technological, philosophical, or mathematical. There are numbers of ways to show why AGI will not be achieved. In this thesis we will concentrate on only two types of challenges that make AGI, in principle, non-achievable: philosophical as well as mathematical challenges.

The reason we will not delve into the technological obstacles is the fact that it will not be necessary to do so. The arguments and their conclusions that will be presented in this thesis should remain valid, no matter how technologically advanced humanity becomes. This means that even if we can solve all technical problems and bypass all technical obstacles on the road to AGI, AGI should in principle, still be non-achievable.

2. The reality of AGI

2.1 What is AGI?

AGI or artificial general intelligence has no agreed upon definition (Goertzel 2014). Although there is no consensus on the definition of AI (Artificial Intelligence) let alone AGI, it is important to mention some proposed definitions, which will help clarify the core of the topic at hand.

Without delving too deeply into the philosophical discussions on definitions, it is important to mention that there are different types of definitions, albeit sometimes they overlap. Examples include stipulative, descriptive, explicative, and ostensive definitions (Gupta and Mackereth 2008). Our aim here is not to define AI or AGI in an Aristotelian fashion by “stating the essence of a thing”, but rather to simply give some clarity to the meaning of the term used, and upon which most researchers in the field can agree on. We can achieve this by defining AGI using descriptive, explicative, and ostensive definitions:

A possible descriptive definition would be:

D1: *“Artificial general intelligence (AGI) can be defined as an AI that has a level of intelligence that is either equivalent to or greater than that of human beings or is able to cope with problems that arise in the world that surrounds human beings with a degree of adequacy at least similar to that of human beings”* (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 11).

The term “AGI” can also be described as:

- a property of certain systems (“AGI” as the intersection of “artificial” (i.e. synthetic) and “generally intelligent”)
- a system that displays this property (an “AGI” meaning “an AGI system”)
- the field of endeavor pursuing the creation of AGI systems, and the study of the nature of AGI

Therefore, roughly speaking, an AGI system can be defined as a synthetic intelligence that has a general scope and is good at generalization across various goals and contexts. (Goertzel 2014, p. 5)

An ostensive definition would be something hypothetical, such as Dolores and other hosts from the American dystopian sci-fi series “Westworld” (2016–2022). The hosts in the Westworld series, particularly Dolores, are AGI agents in a theme park who possess intelligence, the ability to make decisions beyond their programming, adapting to complex environments even outside the theme park in which they were originally developed to stay in, displaying AGI traits.

2.2 Strong vs. Weak AI

There are some other terms used in the AI field which mean similar or even synonymous things to AGI. It is important to note that the arguments in this paper are valid for all the different terms of AGI that are used synonymously. For example, there exist other terms that have the same basic meaning that underlie the expression “AGI”, like for example “*Strong AI*”.

Strong AI usually holds the belief that computers, when appropriately programmed, not only mimic human language and behavior but actually understand and possess mental capacities akin to humans. In this view, such computers genuinely exhibit intelligence in activities like playing chess or understanding languages. In contrast, *Weak AI* represents a more conservative claim that computers are valuable tools in fields like psychology and linguistics, as they can simulate, but not genuinely replicate, human mental abilities.

IBM defines strong AI as the following:

Strong artificial intelligence (AI), also known as artificial general intelligence (AGI) or general AI, is a theoretical form of AI used to describe a certain mindset of AI development. If researchers are able to develop Strong AI, the machine would require an intelligence equal to humans; it would have a self-aware consciousness that has the ability to solve problems, learn, and plan for the future.

Strong AI aims to create intelligent machines that are indistinguishable from the human mind. But just like a child, the AI machine would have to learn through input and experiences, constantly progressing and advancing its abilities over time [...] (IBM 2020).

Consequently, we understand “strong AI”, “general AI” and “AGI” to mean the same thing. Similarly, the AI that currently exists, and which does not meet the conditions of AGI is called “ANI” (Artificial Narrow Intelligence), “weak AI” or just “narrow AI”⁷.

Since “General Intelligence” is a main part of the term we are analyzing, it is also important to briefly cover the debate surrounding the meaning of “intelligence”.

2.3 What is Intelligence?

The definition of “Intelligence” is also highly debated. Intelligence is thought of in different ways and contexts, and can be categorized into different types, such as practical, analytical, creative and emotional intelligence.

Since defining human intelligence is an obstacle in and of itself, it is not surprising that “machine intelligence” or “artificial intelligence” is also difficult to define.

It is enough for our purposes to also give an overall descriptive definition of machine intelligence. Especially popular in the AGI community is the definition proposed by Legg and Hutter. It is the most influential and widely accepted definition. Legg and Hutter wrote a paper in which they enumerated 71 different published definitions of the term “intelligence” and proposed a general definition of intelligence by trying to summarize the most important aspects of these definitions:

“Bringing these key features together gives us what we believe to be the essence of intelligence in its most general form:

⁷ Also referred to as closed world AI.

Intelligence measures an agent's ability to achieve goals in a wide range of environments." (Legg and Hutter 2007a, 2007b).

They then used this definition to come up with a general mathematical formulation of intelligence.

Although this definition gives an overview of what we seemingly understand to be intelligence, it has not gone unchallenged. Some of the criticisms include the fact that these observations, among others, lead to the mathematical concept of universal intelligence. This concept measures an agent's intelligence based on the average rewards it can achieve across various environments, with each environment's complexity influencing its weight in this calculation.

However, this definition encounters issues as it presupposes the presence of a pre-defined reward function (Landgrebe and Smith 2022). In natural organisms, such functions are thought to emerge from a blend of innate tendencies and cultural influences. For artificial systems, the complexity involved in designing a reward function is a significant challenge. At its most extreme, if the reward function were entirely arbitrary, it would render the environment akin to random noise, offering no meaningful patterns for a learning entity to utilize. (Swan et al. 2022, p. 8)

Another critique is that this definition, even within the scope of machine intelligence, is somewhat limiting if we assume (as its authors and other proponents of AGI do) that an intelligent machine should match or surpass human cognitive abilities. Indeed, this definition only addresses one aspect—adaptation to new environments—of Scheler's broader definition of primal intelligence, missing key elements such as spontaneity, lack of prior training, and novelty.

Simultaneously, Hutter's definition is overly inclusive, suggesting that even *C. elegans*, a small worm with just 302 neurons, would be considered intelligent because it can navigate and reproduce in various complex environments (like fruit, vegetable, and mushroom compost, as well as temperate soil, even using snails and slugs for transportation). According to this interpretation, even simple organisms like slime molds or amoebas could be classified as intelligent (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 51).

There is another proposed meaning of intelligence, which is considered to be the current consensus view captured by Linda Gottfredson, where intelligence is “a very general mental capability that, among other things, involves the ability to reason, plan, solve problems, think abstractly, comprehend complex ideas, learn quickly, and learn from experience” (L. Gottfredson 1997).

From now on we will assume the general definition of AGI of D1, where the goal of AGI is to emulate human intelligence to a large extent, where the AI agent is able to cope with human environments to a degree similar to humans.

To achieve this, the AI agent in question has to possess some sort of genuine understanding. Understanding can be seen as a component or manifestation of intelligence. An intelligent entity often demonstrates its intelligence through its capacity to understand complex ideas, solve problems, and learn from experience. Understanding in humans for example involves more than just processing information; it requires the ability to contextualize, interpret, and apply that information in varied, often unforeseen, and novel situations i.e. Complex environments⁸.

For an AGI to exist it must therefore have the ability to general understanding. This is the position of the majority of AGI proponents, and it also follows logically from the tasks imagined to be performed by an AGI.

In the next chapter, however, we will see why computational machines will never realize this attribute, due to their inherent lack of grasping semantics⁹.

⁸ Complex environments have properties which will be discussed when analyzing complex systems in the chapter on mathematical challenges.

⁹ Semantics is the study of meaning.

3. Philosophical Challenges to AGI

There are several different philosophical challenges to the attainability of AGI, some stronger than others. First, we will explain what philosophical arguments we will not use when arguing against AGI¹⁰. Many of the philosophical arguments made against AGI presuppose a certain position in the philosophy of mind, specifically a dualist position.

Dualism is the view that the mind and the body (or the mental and the physical) are fundamentally different kinds of substances or realities. The most famous version of dualism was proposed by René Descartes¹¹, who argued that the mind is a non-physical substance distinct from the body (Robinson 2003).

Physicalism, conversely, is the view that everything that exists is physical in nature, and that mental phenomena are either identical to physical processes or are ultimately explainable in physical terms. This view encompasses several positions, like reductive and non-reductive physicalism, and aims to explain mental processes in terms of brain activity and physical interactions (Stoljar 2001).

It is easy to see why dualists would be more likely to oppose the idea that AGI is achievable. If intelligence, understanding and mental states are non-physical, as dualists believe, then creating AGI—a machine with human-like intelligence and understanding—would be inherently impossible to achieve using physical systems alone. But since machines and computers are just physical systems, it follows that AGI is not possible¹². According to dualism, there is an element of human cognition that is beyond the capabilities of physical computation (Hauser 2020).

¹⁰ A collection of the most popular arguments and their replies can be visited at Hauser 2020.

¹¹ Most modern forms of dualism trace back to Descartes' "Meditations" and the subsequent discussions surrounding his theory. Descartes held a substance dualist view, positing the existence of two distinct types of substance: matter, characterized by its spatial extension, and mind, defined by its capacity for thought. Robinson 2003.

¹² Supposing that AGI would be achieved using computation, as is the view of AGI proponents.

In contrast, physicalists, who believe that everything about the mind and mental states can be explained in physical terms, are more likely to be optimistic about the prospects of creating AGI. They would argue that since all aspects of the mind arise from physical processes, in principle, it should be possible to recreate these processes in a machine.

Other objections are based on the position of vitalism in the philosophy of biology. Vitalists often highlight behaviors of living organisms, arguing that these actions couldn't be explained in the same way as physical processes (Sober 2000, pp. 22–24). Vitalists hold a view similar to substance dualists regarding the mind but to biological organisms in general, positing that a non-material element, a vital force (*Élan vital*)¹³, is at work in living organisms, driving their unique functions and behaviors (Bechtel and Bollhagen 2019).

However, since we want our arguments to be as general as possible, we will not presuppose a dualist or a vitalist position when discussing the achievability of AGI. Both the philosophical challenges as well as the mathematical challenges we consider should be of equal concern to dualists, vitalists as well as physicalists.

3.1 The Chinese Room Argument

None of the known objections have raised as much debate and discussion as the so called “Chinese Room Argument” (CRA) by Searle. It had an impact not just on the AI domain, but in cognitive science and other disciplines as well. This, besides the fact that it is a powerful argument, is why we will delve deeper into this specific argument in this chapter.

Before we dig deeper into the CRA, it is necessary to quickly talk about a phenomenon that is widely spread across AI enthusiasts as well as AGI proponents. We aim to emphasize a widespread

¹³ a term coined by French philosopher Henri Bergson in his 1907 book *Creative Evolution*.

tendency to ascribe intelligence to different artifacts we encounter. This tendency can be summarized in the common saying “Intelligence is in the eye of the beholder”.

Human beings have a strong tendency to anthropomorphize. This occurs when we unconsciously converse with our pets, when children perceive the pre-recorded speech of Furby dolls as truly significant, when individuals mistakenly assign empathetic qualities to voice assistants, or when they confuse a diagram explaining an AI system with its actual programming representation (Ekbia 2008, p. 311). This kind of misconception or illusion, particularly in relation to artifacts, has become known in the field of AI as the *Eliza effect*.

The Eliza effect can be understood as is the tendency to project human traits — such as experience, semantic comprehension or empathy — into computer programs that have a textual interface. Or in other words it is “the susceptibility of people to read far more understanding than is warranted into strings of symbols – especially words – strung together by computers” (Hofstadter 1996, p. 157).

The AI community, frequently without realizing it, has capitalized on this human propensity, transforming what might be termed as innocent anthropomorphism into a professional and often unwarranted technoscientific practice (Risan 1997, p. 57).

This tendency is evident when we casually say things like “the computer is thinking” during a pause in its operation. However, the reality is that the processes within a computer are entirely physical and limited to specific operations defined by Turing and Church in the 1930s. The computer is designed to mimic tasks typically performed by the human mind, leading us to wrongly ascribe similar mental capabilities to the machine, much like we might attribute happiness to a cartoon character (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 11).

John Searle argued in 1992 that while computation in computers is a physical reality, it lacks a mental reality. The meaning we assign to a computer’s actions is dependent on the observer, meaning it’s not an intrinsic property of the machine i.e. it is observer-dependent. This concept is

analogous to the difference between seeing a dollar bill as a mere piece of paper and seeing it as money; without observers, only the physical aspect remains, as the value of money is also observer-dependent (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 11).

We, as humans, experience understanding, but computers do not and, as the argument will show, cannot gain understanding in the future. No matter how sophisticated or impressive our engineered capabilities may become, the aspects of their actions that we interpret as understanding or mentality will always be a result of our observer-dependent perceptions. The implication is that the conscious or mental aspects we might ascribe to computers are not inherent properties of these machines but rather projections of human interpretation.

Can computers programs genuinely understand? Since understanding is crucial for creating intelligence¹⁴ that is at least similar or better than human intelligence. The Chinese Room Argument (CRA) stands as one of the most renowned and extensive debates on a singular topic in contemporary philosophy (Moural 2003). This argument derives its name from a hypothetical scenario introduced by Searle in his 1980 paper, “Minds, Brains, and Programs.”

The discussion surrounding this argument has transcended the confines of philosophy, significantly influencing disciplines such as artificial intelligence and cognitive science (Moural 2003). The Chinese Room Argument aims to demonstrate that the pursuit of strong AI or AGI, as a research endeavor, is fundamentally flawed and cannot achieve success in principle. Which means, regardless of any future improvements in the technology used for AI, AGI will not be achievable.

The argument Searle posed, has been updated and restructured by Searle himself, to clarify the argument and respond to critiques (Searle 1990). The original argument is based on this simplified version of his thought experiment:

¹⁴ From now on I will use “intelligence” as the general intelligence necessary for AGI by definition D1, unless otherwise specified.

1. Imagine a room with an English speaker inside who doesn't know Chinese. This person has a book of rules (in English) for manipulating strings of Chinese characters.

2. People outside the room send in strings of Chinese characters (which are questions in Chinese). The person in the room uses the rule book to find the correct responses to these strings of characters (answers in Chinese) and sends them back out.

3. To an outside observer, it looks like the room can understand and respond to Chinese since the correct answers are being provided. However, the person inside the room does not understand Chinese at all; they're simply following rules to manipulate symbols.

Searle's point is that even if a computer can use rules (like a program or an algorithm) to manipulate symbols (like language) and produce correct answers, this doesn't mean it truly understands the language or has a mind or genuine intelligence for that matter. Just like the person in the room, it's processing information but not "understanding" it in the way humans do. This challenges the idea that mere symbol processing is equivalent to actual thinking or understanding.

This of course applies to all kinds of computers since, if the operator, while running a language program, does not gain an understanding of the language, then it follows that no computer, which only has the same basic capabilities of symbol manipulation that the operator has, could understand the language either.

The crucial point here is the claim that digital computers do not possess any capabilities beyond what Searle has in the thought experiment. In other words, computers, like Searle in the scenario, are only manipulating symbols based on pre-defined rules without any comprehension or awareness of the meaning those symbols represent (Searle et al. 1998, pp. 11–12).

From the thought experiment emerges the argument, which Searle later compresses and it goes like this:

1. Programs are entirely syntactical.
2. Minds have semantics.
3. Syntax is not the same as, nor by itself sufficient for, semantics.

Therefore, programs are not minds. (Searle et al. 1998, p. 11)

Of course, it follows from this that programs cannot understand anything, since understanding something requires some grasp of meaning i.e. semantics.

Fig. 1 *Program Construction*

The argument, although quite simple, has stirred a wide range of debate and responses¹⁵ from all kinds of different disciplines. However, one thing is certain, there is no consensus on where exactly the problem lies in the argument. The criticisms of the Chinese Room argument against Strong AI generally follow three main lines, each varying in how much they concede to the argument (Cole 2004).

Some critics agree that the person in the Chinese Room doesn't understand Chinese but argue that understanding could be generated by the system or a different entity than the individual operating the room. These responses suggest that the room's output could reflect genuine understanding of Chinese, but this understanding doesn't belong to the room operator. They accept Searle's personal lack of understanding but reject his broader claim that no understanding

¹⁵ some include Wilks 1982; Rey 1986; Fisher 1988; Margaret A. Boden 1988 and Hauser 1997.

is created and that computationalism¹⁶ is false (Cole 2004). Examples of this are the *Systems Reply* and *Virtual Mind Reply*.

Other critics accept Searle's assertion that merely running a language processing program doesn't create understanding in either humans or computer systems. However, they propose that variations of the computer system, such as a robot interacting with the physical world or a system simulating a human brain's operations, might indeed achieve understanding (Cole 2004). Examples of this are the *Brain Simulator Reply* as well as the *Robot Reply*.

The final group of critics doesn't even concede to the narrow argument against AI presented in the CRA. They suggest that the man in the room might actually understand Chinese despite Searle's denial, or that the scenario itself is flawed. Arguments here include questioning the reliability of intuitions in such hypothetical scenarios, redefining what it means to "understand," and challenging the assumption that any system can run any computer program. Some critics also argue for attributing understanding based on observable behavior, as we do with humans and would do with other intelligent beings, aligning with Turing's perspective on machine intelligence (Cole 2004).

Many of the replies have been responded to by Searle himself in a number of different publications (Searle 1980; Searle 1990). We will only consider some of the most popular and arguably strongest replies to the argument and see if it is enough to deem this argument as unsound. This will include the *Systems Reply*, the *Virtual Mind Reply* as well as the *Robot Reply*.

3.1.1 The Systems Reply

Ned Block, along with several other prominent thinkers such as Jack Copeland, Daniel Dennett, Douglas Hofstadter, Jerry Fodor, John Haugeland, Ray Kurzweil, and Georges Rey, were early

¹⁶ Computationalism or the computational theory of mind (CTM) is the position in the philosophy of mind that the mind itself is a computational system Rescorla 2015.

advocates of the Systems Reply (Cole 2004).

The Systems Reply is therefore possibly the most popular as well as the strongest counterargument to the CRA. It posits that while an individual component of the system (like Searle) may not understand Chinese, this does not necessarily mean the system as a whole lacks understanding. It suggests that understanding should not be sought solely in the individual operating the room but rather in the entire system, of which the operator is just a part. That means that the whole system, including the room, the book of symbols as well as Searle himself, understand Chinese. In this context, Georges Rey posited that the individual in the Chinese Room serves only a role analogous to a computer's central processing unit (CPU) within the overall system (Rey 1986).

This counterargument is problematic on different levels, and Searle responds to it in a number of different publications. We can divide our response to the systems reply into two types of responses, a general and a specific response.

We will start with the specific response. The systems reply can be challenged by slightly editing the thought experiment and convert it into an outdoor version of the CRA. In this thought experiment the English speaker is not inside a room but outdoors. He also does not use a book of symbol manipulation, since he has memorized the complete instruction manual.

The operator memorizes all the rules and learns to recognize and write Chinese characters, enabling him to function without the physical room. In that case, the English speaker/operator has absorbed the whole system. But even in that case, the issue still remains, the operator does not understand any Chinese. Searle's main point in response to the Systems Reply is that even if the entire process of symbol manipulation is internalized within the operator, it still doesn't result in genuine understanding (Smith 2003, pp. 214–260).

Now let us consider the general response to the systems reply. For that, let us again consider the core points of the CRA. The core argument is that the formal or abstract operations of a computer

program alone cannot ensure the presence of mental or semantic content crucial for human cognition. While a system might possess semantic content for other reasons, the claim that a specific program implementation in certain hardware might cause consciousness deviates from AGI's principle. AGI proponents maintain that the type of hardware does not matter as long as it can support the program, emphasizing the sufficiency of the program itself for cognition, independent of the hardware used.

The CRA is based on two key logical principles that remain unshaken despite years of debate. Firstly, computer syntax doesn't equate to semantics; a computer's formal program doesn't inherently possess or guarantee semantic understanding. Secondly, simulating a process is not the same as replicating it. While computers can simulate various processes, including cognitive functions, this does not mean they genuinely possess consciousness or mental capabilities. For instance, simulating digestion doesn't mean a computer can actually digest food, just like simulating consciousness doesn't mean it actually experiences it (Preston and Bishop 2023).

The advocates of the systems reply are usually reductionists. Reductionism in this context posits that all biological systems, like organisms, are fundamentally composed of molecules and their interactions. This concept aligns with metaphysical physicalism, which in a biological context suggests that (a) biological properties are dependent on, or supervene on, physical properties, meaning any change in a biological property implies a change in an underlying physical property, and (b) each specific biological process is essentially the same as some physico-chemical process, a view known as token-token reduction (Brigandt and Love 2008).

The problem with this view is not its adherence to physicalism per se, but that it reduces all emergent properties and behavior to some of the systems parts. In the context of AGI, it reduces intelligence to the symbol manipulation of a program.

However, this causes a contradiction in the way they try to refute the CRA. They assert that mental states are just symbol manipulations, but in cases like the Chinese Room, where mere symbol manipulation clearly lacks understanding, they suggest that understanding must exist elsewhere

in the system. This stance contradicts the initial claim that symbol manipulation alone constitutes mental states. Thus, the reductionist view struggles to reconcile the distinction between mere symbol manipulation and genuine semantic understanding.

Searle points this out by saying:

[..] The problem for all these forms of reductionism is the same: are there really two things or just one. The thesis of reductionism is that there is just one thing- behavior, or computer programs or sense data or whatever-but in the face of the counter-examples the reductionist says that the other thing must be there too. Hence there are two things. The urge of the reductionist to try to hang on to the reduced notion amounts to a quiet abandonment of the reduction (Preston and Bishop 2023, p. 54).

The only way to get out of this conflict and stay consistent, is for the reductionist to say that there is nothing more to symbol manipulation, namely there is no such thing as *understanding*¹⁷. Only symbol manipulation exists in all systems, whether artificial or biological. It is however, especially from a first-person perspective, blatantly absurd to equate manipulating symbols in a language one understands, like English, whilst understanding them, to manipulating symbols in a language one doesn't understand, like Chinese, without any comprehension (Preston and Bishop 2023).

3.1.2 The Virtual Minds Reply

The Virtual Minds Reply (VMR) to the Chinese Room argument, like the Systems Reply, agrees that the room operator does not understand Chinese just by running the paper machine. However, the VMR focuses on the creation of understanding, irrespective of the operator's comprehension. It proposes that a functioning system might generate new, virtual entities capable of understanding,

¹⁷ Searle writes: "Strong AI is a weird mixture of behaviorism and dualism. It is behaviorist in its acceptance of the Turing Test, but it is at a much more fundamental philosophical level, dualist, because it rejects the idea that consciousness and intentionality are ordinary biological phenomena like digestion. In the words of Dennett and Hofstadter, we are to think of the mind as, "an abstract sort of thing whose identity is independent of any particular physical embodiment"" Searle 2023.

which are distinct from both the system as a whole and its individual components, like the CPU or operator. This virtual entity could understand Chinese, separate from the operator and the entire system. The VMR contends that the psychological characteristics of any artificially created mind, including language skills, are determined by the program and database, and are not identical to the traits of the CPU or the paper machine operator (Cole 2004).

The argument suggests that the main issue with the Chinese Room Argument is its framing of Strong AI claims as “the computer understands Chinese” or “the System understands Chinese,” whereas the relevant claim for AI should be whether “the running computer creates understanding of Chinese”. Essentially, the VMR posits that Searle’s evidence, which is based on his own lack of understanding in the room, doesn’t refute a rephrased but equally potent AI claim about the potential of programmed digital computers to create understanding (Cole 2004). The VMR has been defended by (Hayes et al. 1992; David J. Chalmers 2014; Block 2006) and others.

The problem with this reply is that it tries to separate the property or attribute (understanding) from the subject holding that property (the computer). This is unreasonable since the attribute of understanding cannot be imagined floating independently from the subject with this quality of understanding. The notion that a running computer “creates understanding” is meaningless, since it is similar to saying that a human body creates consciousness but is itself unconscious. The important question would still remain: Does this human being possess consciousness or not? In our case the question would be: Does the computer program possess understanding or not?

It seems like the VMR is an equivocation of sorts, shifting the actual discussion from the fundamental nature of understanding in AGI, to a speculative notion of virtual entities. This shift redirects the focus from assessing whether the system itself has genuine cognitive abilities, to a hypothetical scenario where “understanding” is attributed to abstract constructs within the system.

3.1.3 The Robot Reply

The Robot Reply acknowledges that a computer in a confined room, as in Searle's Chinese Room scenario, cannot understand language or meaning. It suggests that real understanding might be achieved by placing a computer inside a robot equipped with sensors and effectors, allowing it to interact with and learn from the world, much like a child does. Proponents like Margaret Boden, Tim Crane, and others support this view, arguing that meaningful connections to the external world can endow internal symbols with semantic content. This concept aligns with the ideas of wide content or externalist semantics, accepting Searle's point that mere internal syntax is insufficient for understanding, while emphasizing the role of external interactions in creating meaningful language comprehension (Cole 2004).

Searle responds to the Robot Reply by asserting that it is not much different from the Systems Reply. He contends that adding sensors to provide extra input to a computer would only result in additional syntactic, not semantic, information. To illustrate this, he modifies the Chinese Room scenario: Imagine the man inside the room also receives binary digits from sensors like a video camera, and his instructions include using these digits along with Chinese characters. Searle argues this still wouldn't enable the man to understand the meaning of the Chinese characters; it would merely increase his syntactical processing workload (Searle 1988, 1987).

Furthermore, it is important to note that we would be talking about a robot, which by definition would still be based entirely on programs which are themselves again based on mere syntactical manipulation. The Robot Reply would have substance if we would be talking about an entity which is not a robot i.e. based on syntactical manipulation alone but has different properties that are sufficient to casually create the emergence of understanding, a project that evidently diverges from that of AGI.

It is understood that the specific neurobiological processes occurring in the brain are capable of generating understanding, intentionality, and other aspects of our mental experiences. This happens through a type of causation that works from the more basic biological level upwards i.e.

“bottom-up” causation. A program, however, is described not by its ability to generate the system’s higher-level attributes, since it lacks this capability. Instead, it is characterized by its syntactical or formal structure (Searle 2023, p. 55).

This means even if a robot had enhanced “perceptual” and “motor” abilities, and functioned impressively in the world, it would still lack true understanding. Such a robot, even if it could pass the most sophisticated Turing Test, wouldn’t exhibit actual psychological phenomena. This is because genuine mental states can’t be caused solely through external interactions, and since this interaction itself would be, again, mere syntactical manipulation (Preston 2006, p. 32).

Of course, there are other replies to the CRA, such as the many mansions reply, other minds reply, and the brain simulator reply. But all of these replies seem to deviate from the core of the original CRA, and have also been thoroughly responded to by Searle and others (Preston and Bishop 2023; Smith 2003).

3.1.4 Does the CRA assume a dualist position?

Some opponents to the CRA claim that the argument is based on the assumption of dualism.

For example (Hauser 2020) writes :

“The Chinese room experiment fails because acceptance of its putative result – that the person in the room doesn’t understand – already presupposes the dualist hypothesis over computationalism or mind-brain identity theory.”

This is not true however, and to show why, we can simply use a counterexample.

Formally, the premise of Hauser is a conditional statement: $A \rightarrow B$ (“if A then B”).

Where **A** is “accepting the CRA” and **B** is “assuming a dualist position”.

But since we can demonstrate that $A \wedge \neg B$ is true, we refute the claim that $A \rightarrow B$ because we would have shown that A can occur even in the absence of B.

The counterexample would simply be the fact that someone can be a physicalist and still accept the CRA's conclusions. The physicalist might argue that the complexity of the brain's physical processes is what gives rise to understanding, a complexity that current computer programs or AI systems do not possess. Therefore, even while accepting that brain functions are physical, the physicalist can still maintain that current AI, which operates at a much simpler physical level, does not achieve true understanding or intelligence as seen by humans. The syntax manipulation by programs on a Turing machine is simply not sufficient enough to cause understanding to emerge.

As we have seen, the CRA is a simple yet powerful argument against the possibility of strong AI or AGI. When contemplating the most popular replies we see that the systems reply does not hold when simply but slightly altering the setting of the experiment, such that the operator is outdoors and has memorized the instruction manual and consequently absorbing the system.

Similarly, when pondering the robot reply, adding sensors and cameras to a computer would only result in extra input which would then again be additional syntactic, not semantic, information. When entertaining the VMR we see that it is an equivocation, shifting the discussion from the fundamental nature of understanding in AGI, to a speculative notion of virtual entities, where neither the components nor the system as a whole understands.

And finally, we have shown that the CRA is not a dualist argument, since it is perfectly reasonable to be a physicalist and still deem the CRA to be a sound argument, without contradicting the physicalist assumptions in the philosophy of mind (Preston 2006, pp. 254–255).

4. Mathematical Challenges to AGI:

When talking about AGI we naturally presuppose the creation of machine/ computational general intelligence, since this is what the AGI community assumes is achievable. Therefore, we will focus our discussion on why achieving general intelligence using computational methods is not possible. In this context, AGI is described as a technology implemented through computers. To show why this is mathematically impossible, irrespective of the technological advancements we may make in the hardware of computers, we will delve into some basics of how AI works as well as the theory of complex systems.

We will discuss why modeling/emulating human intelligence using computers is not possible and why modern approaches (such as neural networks) will also fail in this mission. The core concepts of this argument – complex systems theory against AGI achievability - are primarily based on insights from (Landgrebe and Smith 2022). Artificial intelligence agents are computational algorithms designed to either mimic certain behaviors observed in the human brain or to perform functions useful for humans in various settings. To comprehend these AI agents, it's necessary to understand the principles of modeling, computable algorithms, and the dynamics of complex systems.

Let us start by looking at the principles of computability.

4.1 The Church-Turing Thesis

When models run on computers, they take the form of algorithms that must be computable to be executable. Computability, in an intuitive sense, means that an algorithm can process an input to produce an output effectively and automatically, without any human input like decision-making or intuition. This is crucial for the concept of general AI, which aims to replace certain human activities rather than just supplementing them (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 115).

The formal definition of computability was established over 80 years ago by Alonzo Church and Alan Turing, the so-called “*Church-Turing-Thesis*”. Although they used different methods, their definitions were mathematically equivalent. According to the Church-Turing thesis, an algorithm is computable if it can be formulated as a sequence of elementary recursive functions¹⁸.

The Church-Turing Thesis asserts that any calculation or computational process that can be performed algorithmically (i.e., by following a set of well-defined rules or procedures) can also be performed by a Turing machine. This part of the thesis establishes the Turing machine as a universal model of computation, capable of executing any algorithm (Copeland 1997).

Conversely, the thesis also implies that anything that can be computed by a Turing machine can be expressed as an algorithm. Since Turing machines are designed to simulate the basic operations of algorithmic computation, any process they can carry out can, in principle, be translated into an algorithm.

This bidirectional nature of the Church-Turing Thesis is foundational in computer science, as it helps define the boundaries of what is computable in a very general sense. It means that the realm of problems solvable by a Turing machine is essentially the same as the realm of problems solvable by any conceivable algorithmic process (Copeland 1997).

In the realm of AI, this means that AI solutions must be derived from mathematical functions that are computable in the Church-Turing sense. This restricts the types of programs a computer can execute to those based on mathematical models whose outputs are computable from their inputs. These models represent aspects of reality and are often used to simulate or predict real-world systems (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 116). However, any mathematical model running on a Turing machine can only adequately model what is termed “logic systems”¹⁹.

Logic Systems are systems with nearly exact models that can both explain and predict their

¹⁸ These are: the constant, successor, and identity functions as well as the composition operator and primitive recursion. For more info see appendix A.a

¹⁹ Terminology used by Landgrebe and Smith 2022.

behavior. They are characterized by three main properties: (i) the dominance of one of the four fundamental interactions²⁰, (ii) uniform and isotropic interactions, and (iii) stable boundary conditions. These systems are referred to as logic systems because their behavior can be comprehensively understood and predicted using logical principles in conjunction with *extended Newtonian mathematics*²¹ (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 312).

This is because to be computable, a model must align with an algorithm expressible using elementary recursive Church functions. Although these models can approximate complex systems, they operate as processes within the logic system of the computer, not as subsystems of the complex systems they mimic. They create a mathematical image, mapping from the complex system space to a logic system space (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 115–116).

4.2 What is Modeling?

Every scientific model represents a model of reality. We can understand a model as “a representation of an aspect of reality that uses abstract symbols (such as mathematical equations, or drawings or sketches, or physical structures such as an orrery or an architect’s physical model of a building) in order to describe, explain, or predict the aspect of reality in question” (Landgrebe and Smith 2022; Hesse 1970).

We can imagine models as abstractions of phenomena, whilst phenomena are real, theories of these phenomena aim at truth, models are something in between. Models act as intermediaries, extracting certain elements from real-world phenomena and linking them to the governing theories through simplified mathematical structures (Hacking 1986, p. 217).

²⁰ also known as fundamental forces: gravitational force, electromagnetic force, weak nuclear force, strong nuclear force. This is important so that the other forces can be easily neglected.

²¹ The term was used by Landgrebe and Smith 2022 and it refers to the traditional differential calculus, enhanced by areas like statistical mechanics and differential geometry, along with their uses. This enhancement is further supported by the general theory of relativity, as well as some techniques employed in artificial intelligence, including propositional and predicate logic, and graph theory.

4.3 Types of Models

There are many different types of models which can be categorized into different types of categories. We can categorize models based on the kind of objects that are being modeled, for example, models of physical objects or fictional and abstract objects (Frigg and Hartmann 2006). Or they can be categorized based on their function, like descriptive, explanatory or predictive models (Hesse 1980).

The most effective models we know of are those created by humans, such as engineered artifacts. These models are usually predictive models. The term “predictive”, extends beyond the mere forecasting of future events. In mathematical modeling, “predict” broadly means computing an output from an input. For instance, in spam detection algorithms, identifying spam is considered a prediction. Similarly, in language generation algorithms like automated customer response systems, the production of an appropriate response is also a form of prediction (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 110).

Prediction in modeling refers to accurately forecasting a system’s behavior based on a given input. Predictive models, which can be exact or approximative, assure that the output aligns with the actual system’s behavior. Exact models use precise equations, while approximative models are stochastic, like those predicting dice outcomes. Stochastic models, including statistical learning models and deep neural networks, typically provide approximate predictions. This approach encompasses both precise and probabilistic methods to model various systems (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 111–112).

Models can also be used to either *simulate* or *emulate* a certain phenomenon.

The objective of a simulation is to comprehend the impact of alterations in inputs or model parameters on the system’s output. For instance, in medical training, simulations are used for practicing surgeries and emergency response, as well as modeling the spread of diseases in

epidemiology or in aviation, to train pilots in various flying conditions and scenarios without the risk of actual flying.

Emulation is the process where the behavior of one entity (like a brain, an organism, or a river) is replicated by a different entity, such as through computer programs or robots for human behavior. The essence of an emulation lies in creating a model that mimics the response of the emulated entity to similar inputs. Its main objective is to replicate behavior, with the model reacting to specific inputs in ways that closely resemble how the original entity would behave under analogous conditions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 114). An example would be software that emulates human voice, used in virtual assistants and speech generation tools for people with speech impairments.

It is important to understand that for achieving AGI it would not be sufficient to *simulate* human intelligence, but to *emulate*²² human intelligence. This is because a simulation does not *generate* AGI, it simply simulates it. While emulation means we have an actual entity that possesses AGI similar to that of human intelligence. The distinction is clear when we consider the achievement of an artificial heart.

A simulation of an artificial heart is not an achievement of an artificial heart, because the mere simulation does not cause an artificial heart to pump blood, it just simulates the pumping of blood. While an emulation of the human heart artificially would be achieving an artificial heart that actually pumps, i.e., it causes the blood to pump (Preston and Bishop 2023, p. 56). Similarly, we would need to emulate human intelligence to be able to confidently say that we have achieved AGI.

²² We could also use the word “duplicate”

Fig. 2 (Diagram showing obstacles in every step of modeling and emulating complex systems using differential calculus)

4.4 Limits of Modeling

We will now focus on mathematical obstacles regarding the creation of AGI. The main issue we will be concerned about is the fact that we can mathematically only model what we called “logic systems”. To be able to emulate human intelligence, we would need to be able to model the human nervous system, which is a complex system.

The issue does not stop there, however, even the computation of theoretical complex system model would not be possible, this is due to the fact that what we understand to be computation is only done on so called “Turing Machines”. These machines, which include all computers in the world, are also limited to the computation of logic systems.

This means we cannot emulate complex systems since 1. Our paradigm of mathematics cannot model complex phenomena, and 2. Due to the definition of what we understand as computers.

It is important to note that the second point is not an issue of technology as much as it is an issue of theoretical computation. This means that any computer, no matter how advanced, will still not be able to compute models of complex systems.

For this we need to have a quick dive into the theory of complex systems.

4.5 What is a System?

A system is defined as a collection of dynamically interrelated elements. The behavior of a system, which embodies this dynamic interrelationship, may not always be directly observable but always has observable outcomes, either directly or through instruments. The process of defining a system involves delimitation, where specific elements, their types, interactions, and observable outcomes are selected. This delimitation sets the system’s boundaries and granularity levels. Subsystems, which are part of a larger system, are also defined through further delimitations, each having behaviors that contribute to the larger system’s overall behavior (Landgrebe and Smith 2022,

p. 117).

4.6 Difference Between Logic Systems and Complex Systems

In this context we distinguish between two types of systems: logic systems and complex systems. We have already shortly defined what a logic system is. Accordingly, a complex system is a system that does not meet the conditions of the logic system, and that has certain specific properties that, when combined, deem a system to be a complex system. We will come to these properties in what follows.

This distinction is important since, based on the type of system we are analyzing, we can generate an adequate mathematical model or not. We can usually model logic systems mathematically, maybe some aspects of complex systems, but never complete complex systems. Why that is the case will also be explained later.

Now we can present the general reason behind why AGI is not achievable mathematically. The general argument against AGI achievability from a mathematical perspective can be depicted as follows:

- P1: Complex systems fundamentally differ from logic systems.
- P2: Achieving AGI necessitates adequate modeling of complex systems²³.
- P3: Logic systems cannot adequately model complex systems.
- P4: Our computational capabilities are limited to logic systems²⁴.
- P5: Our mathematical modeling is confined to logic systems²⁵.
- C: Therefore, AGI is unattainable.

We can further compress the argument to the following:

²³ Such as the modeling of human or general intelligence for complex environments

²⁴ According to the Church-Turing Thesis.

²⁵ Due to our paradigm of extended Newtonian mathematics.

P1: Achieving AGI necessitates adequate modeling of complex systems.

P2: Logic systems cannot adequately model complex systems.

P3: We can only model Logic systems

C: AGI cannot be achieved.

Symbolically the argument would be:

P1: $A \rightarrow M$

P2: $\neg L$

P3: $M \rightarrow L$

$\therefore C: \neg A$

While:

A represents "Achieving AGI"

M represents "Adequate modeling of complex systems"

And L represents "Adequate modeling using logic systems"

Since $\neg L$ (from P2), and according to P3: $M \rightarrow L$, the contrapositive of P3 is $\neg L \rightarrow \neg M$. And since it is the case that $\neg M$ it follows that $\neg A$ (the contrapositive of P1).

4.7 The Theory of Complex Systems

The theory of complex systems is a fairly recent approach within the scientific enterprise. The concept of which is often regarded as a novel unifying framework for science, revolutionizing our comprehension of systems whose behavior has been challenging to predict and control, like that of the human brain and the global economy (Ladyman et al. 2013).

The history of the theory of complex systems is marked by a gradual shift from linear and reductionist approaches in science to a recognition of the interconnectedness and dynamical nature of various systems, whether natural, social, or artificial.

Especially in the realm of the philosophy of science, the theory of complex systems holds significant interest. There has been substantial engagement from philosophers, resulting in intriguing perspectives and understandings concerning different facets of these systems²⁶.

Although the theory of complex systems may still be in its infancy, the fundamental building blocks have been established. And despite skepticism about the comprehensibility of complex systems, the field is showing promising clarity. Fundamental aspects, including dynamical multilayer networks, scaling laws, algorithmic dynamics in statistical mechanics, and concepts of evolution, co-evolution, and information theory, are becoming increasingly defined.

The aim of introducing the theory of complex systems is to show that these systems cannot be mathematically modeled and are therefore impossible to emulate. We will show that human biological brains, which we would need to emulate to create AGI, are complex systems.

Complex systems can generally be defined as “co-evolving multilayer networks” (Turner et al. 2019, p. 22). These systems have special properties that make them fall under the umbrella of complex systems. Unlike the usual systems that we can accurately or probabilistically predict using equations from mathematics and physics, these systems either lack some fundamental properties that make them calculable or predictable or exhibit certain properties that make them incalculable and unpredictable. We will investigate some of these properties in what is to come, but first, it is helpful to present an example of a model of a physical phenomenon of a simple logic system.

²⁶ See e.g. Rescher 1998; Gabbay 2011 Wimsatt 1994; Rihani 2002 and Mitchell 2011; Weaver 1948; Bertalanffy 1972.

4.8 Example using Newtons Second Law of Motion

An example of a simple logic system²⁷ is from classical mechanics, the simple phenomenon of dropping a stone.

Newton formulated the famous formula, which is also called Newton's second law or Newton's law of motion:

$$m \cdot d^2x/dt^2 = F(x),$$

where t is time, $x(t)$ is the trajectory, m is the mass of the stone, and $F(x)$ is the force acting on the stone. The derivative is a fundamental concept in calculus, to which we will turn in greater detail later, it measures how a quantity changes over time.

In our case d^2x/dt^2 is the second derivative of position x with respect to time t . The first derivative would be dx/dt and would signify the velocity of the object. The derivative of the velocity gives us the acceleration a of the object. This means $d^2x/dt^2 = a$. Which results in the general formula of $F(x) = m \cdot a$. If we consider the force to be due to gravity, then $F(x) = m \cdot g$, where g is the acceleration due to gravity.

Initial conditions refer to the specific parameters at the beginning of the observation, usually at time $t=0$, In the context of Newton's Second Law, these typically include the object's initial position $x(0) = x_0$ and initial velocity $v(0) = v_0$. Similarly, boundary conditions can be set for solving a specific problem in classical mechanics.

The simple logic system is then ready to be calculated and accurately predict the information of any stone, given we know the information of the rest of the variables. Predictive implies that, fundamentally, it is possible to solve these equations. The key is to ensure that we have as many independent equations as unknowns to solve the problem.

²⁷ i.e. non-complex system.

Note that in this example of a simple logic system we can ignore all context of the phenomenon and all other variables that exist (such as air resistance) surrounding the phenomenon, and still be able to accurately predict the phenomenon. This is not the case with complex systems as we will come to see.

4.9 The Properties of Complex Systems

Complex systems show a number of unique properties that demarcate them from simple logic systems. We will shortly summarize these properties without delving too much into the details of each one²⁸.

1: Change and evolutionary character

Complex systems are characterized by their dynamic nature and evolutionary behavior. They exhibit changes that can be sudden and unpredictable, involving the transformation of element types and their combinations. This includes changes in the behaviors of all instances of a type within the system. A key aspect of these systems is their creative capacity, allowing for the constant generation of new elements and novel patterns of interaction. This evolutionary and creative trait is central to the complexity and adaptability of such systems.

2: Element-dependent interactions

The second property of complex systems is element-dependent interactions, which result in irregularity and non-repeatability. This means that the system's behavior does not conform to predictable patterns that can be captured in equations, emphasizing its irregular nature. Additionally, its behavior is non-repeatable, indicating that it cannot be consistently reproduced under experimental conditions. This property underscores the unique and often unpredictable nature of interactions within complex systems, contributing to their dynamic and diverse behaviors.

²⁸ For a more in depth explanation of these properties see Thurner et al. 2019, pp. 1–26 and Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 126–139.

3: Force overlay

The third property involves the overlay of multiple forces acting simultaneously within the system, which may interact with each other. This often correlates with anisotropy, meaning the effects of these force overlays don't spread equally in all directions. The result is a varying magnitude of impact across different parts of the system, contributing to its complex behavior and making its dynamics even more intricate.

4: Non-ergodic phase spaces

The fourth property of complex systems is the presence of non-ergodic phase spaces, which leads to unpredictability based on the system's elements and results in time-irreversibility. This means that the processes within the system cannot be accurately described by time-symmetric equations. In such systems, a reversal of the time direction does not yield identical or reversible outcomes, emphasizing their inherently irreversible nature over time²⁹.

5: Drivenness

The fifth property, drivenness, pertains to complex systems either being influenced by an external energy source or having an inherent internal drive. This characteristic indicates the absence of a stable equilibrium state that the system continually moves toward. Instead, the presence of an energy gradient prevents equilibrium, leading to the dissipation of energy within the system. This property highlights the dynamic and non-static nature of complex systems, constantly influenced by or responding to energy variations.

6: Context-dependence

The sixth property is context-dependence, which refers to the complex system's non-fixed boundary conditions and its embeddedness in one or more broader environments. This means that the system's behavior and characteristics are significantly influenced by external factors and its surroundings, making it sensitive to and integrated with its environment. Such context-dependence further adds to the complexity of the system, as its dynamics are not solely

²⁹ We will revisit non-ergodicity and phase space later when discussing problems of modeling complex systems.

determined internally but are also shaped by external interactions and conditions.

7: Chaos

The seventh property is chaos, characterized by the unpredictability of the system's behavior due to the impossibility of obtaining exact measurements of initial conditions. This property highlights the inherent difficulty in predicting how the system will evolve over time, owing to the sensitive dependence on initial states, which are often too complex or imprecise to be measured accurately.

4.10 Human Intelligence as a Complex System

The human organism is an intricate complex system composed of numerous subsystems at various levels of granularity. Each multicellular organism is a highly complex, relatively isolated system containing many hierarchically ordered and variously situated subsystems. These subsystems are both interconnected and segregated, allowing them to function undisturbed while regulating their behavior in coordination with associated systems (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 128).

Specifically, the human cognitive system consists of billions of neurons, each containing a vast array of molecular elements. A standard neuron is composed of approximately 100 trillion atoms, which together constitute around 100 thousand distinct varieties of RNA molecules (Wu et al. 2014). Changes in the nervous system, such as the formation of new memories or synapses, lead to new types of elements and relationships, underpinning the range of human behavioral and cognitive dispositions.

Human cognitive activity often occurs within a social context, forming even more complex systems where individuals interact and influence each other. Learning new skills, for instance, can alter the dynamics of these social systems. This reflects how changes in individual elements (humans) can impact the overall social system.

This complexity contrasts sharply with simpler systems like the solar system. When an asteroid gets caught in a planet's gravitational pull and starts orbiting it, the solar system gains a new element but not a new type of element or interaction, nor does it experience a change in its context-independence. This illustrates the stark difference in complexity and dynamism between biological, particularly human, systems and more straightforward physical systems like the solar system (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 128).

Animate complex systems, despite their intricate nature, exhibit a high degree of organization and stability, which is essential for their survival and reproduction. This stability has enabled a continuous genetic lineage from the earliest living organisms to present-day humans and other species. A key aspect of this stability is their ability to react appropriately to the behavior of other complex systems within their environments, a capability that is crucial for their survival.

However, the biological basis of this ability remains poorly understood. The underlying causality that organizes living systems and integrates them into a cohesive system remains elusive. This is primarily due to the complex nature of these systems and their interactions, which makes them challenging to fully comprehend (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 143).

4.11 Why We Need to Model Complex Systems for AGI

To remind ourselves again with the definition of AGI which we use :

D1: "Artificial general intelligence (AGI) can be defined as an AI that has a level of intelligence that is either equivalent to or greater than that of human beings or is able to cope with problems that arise in the world that surrounds human beings with a degree of adequacy at least similar to that of human beings" (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 11) .

For an AI agent to cope with problems and situations that arise in the world that surrounds human beings with a degree of adequacy at least similar to that of human beings, it must have the ability to adapt to the complex environments that surround human beings.

Let's assume there will be numerous AI definitions and implementations developed in the future. Their common feature will be the necessity for AI agents to interact with an open environment, our surrounding world. Our world is comprised of complex systems, some non-living like weather, tides, or seismic movements, and others living, including all human and animal behaviors. Consequently, any AI agent, regardless of its definition, must contend with an environment shaped by these complex systems (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 59–60).

To achieve this goal we would naturally need an AI agent to mimic the behavior of intelligent beings such as ourselves. But to develop a software emulation that mimics a system's behavior, it is necessary to construct a mathematical model of that system which can accurately predict its behavior (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. xi).

We demonstrate that achieving this is unfeasible due to a fundamental limit on what machines can process. This limitation is not determined by the technological constraints of computers, but rather by the inherent boundaries in the capabilities of mathematical modeling.

But as we will see, intelligent beings such as us, as well as animals and biological organisms in general, are not mathematically modellable due to their inherent properties as complex systems. We can only model logic systems, yet only complex systems can adequately adapt to complex environments. For example, no single instance exists of end-to-end deep neural networks (dNNs) demonstrating complex behavior in new environments that are comparable to the complex behavior observed in vertebrates, much less in human beings (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 57).

If we cannot -in principle- emulate even the simplest of complex systems, then it follows that the emulation of a complicated complex system is plainly unthinkable. To show why we cannot adequately model complex systems, we will elaborate some of the reasons from a mathematical perspective.

4.12 Limits of Modeling Complex Systems

There are many reasons why we cannot model complex systems mathematically, but for our purpose it is sufficient to focus only on the limitations of modeling using our current paradigm of mathematics, the paradigm of extended Newtonian mathematics.

It is important to note that when we talk about modeling complex systems, we mean by that the adequate modeling of that system using computation. By “adequately”, we mean modeling the system in a way that satisfies the requirements which the model was created to satisfy. Typically, in the field of artificial intelligence, these criteria are necessary for dependable automation or the recognition of patterns (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 152).

The fundamental concepts of mathematics, on which all models of physical phenomena rely, are the concepts of calculus. Calculus is the branch of mathematics that deals with rates of change (differential calculus) and accumulation of quantities (integral calculus). These concepts of calculus were independently developed by both Newton and Leibnitz in the 17th century. Their work, especially on the methods of differential equations opened the door for a new paradigm of explaining and predicting physical phenomena and with it started the study of classical mechanics.

Although Newton wasn’t the initial inventor of differentiation, integration, or the first to understand how these processes are connected in the fundamental theorem of calculus, he did succeed, however, in providing a unification of these concepts into a universal algorithm that could be applied to all types of functions, including both algebraic and transcendental³⁰ ones (Boyer and Merzbach 2011, p. 365).

Differential calculus is crucial in designing and managing many of the systems around us, like pumps, drainage, dams, and air conditioning, which have all become essential for our daily life. It enables precise predictions and control over such systems. Additionally, differential calculus is key

³⁰ Transcendental functions are usually more complex than algebraic functions, such as e^x , $\ln(x)$, $\arcsin(x)$ etc.

in astrophysics and space exploration. It allows us not just to predict the movement of celestial bodies, but also to design and steer spacecraft through the cosmos, using calculations for thrust derived from the ideal rocket equation (Perko 2014).

Efforts to model complex systems using differential calculus have been diverse, encompassing various deterministic as well as stochastic adaptations and extensions of this mathematical tool.

4.13 Deterministic vs. Stochastic Modeling

In the field of computable system models, there are two fundamental types of models: deterministic and stochastic. Deterministic models operate under a fixed set of rules, leading to predictable outcomes based on initial conditions. These include systems like propositional logic, predicate logic or modal logic where outcomes are strictly governed by predefined logic (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 146).

Stochastic models, in contrast, incorporate randomness and probability, making them suitable for situations where uncertainty plays a key role, like in financial markets or weather forecasting. The choice between deterministic and stochastic models depends on the system's complexity and the presence of uncertain elements. We will examine both types of models starting with deterministic models.

4.14 Deterministic Models

When talking about deterministic models we usually mean differential equation models and their variants. These models can be utilized to precisely represent the alterations in systems with multiple variables when the connections between these variables adhere to deterministic patterns, similar to those observed in the physical world.

Today we use the notations of Leibnitz to formulate our differential equations, but they essentially describe the same processes as these of Newton. There are however conditions that must be satisfied to be able to make use of differential equations to model certain phenomena.

The first condition is the fact that the phenomenon represented be *continuous* (Nandakumaran and Datti 2020). This means they should be depictable on graphs as either straight lines, smooth curves, or manifolds. Examples include flow of water in a river, movement of a planet in its orbit or change in atmospheric pressure or temperature over time.

The second condition is the fact that there must be *a limited number of interacting variables* in the phenomena being modeled. Simple physical systems modeled by ordinary differential equations have only one variable. Systems modeled by partial differential equations (PDEs) usually have 2 variables, sometimes more but usually not more than a few. PDEs with more than 5 variables become generally impossible to solve (Nandakumaran and Datti 2020).

The two conditions mentioned above can be thought of as necessary conditions for modeling phenomena using differential calculus. These conditions, however, pose a difficulty when trying to model complex systems. Regarding the first condition, complex systems are usually discontinuous, and exhibit abrupt behavior. These systems display sudden changes, non-linear dynamics, that clash with the condition of continuity needed by differential calculus. An example would be an animal adapting to new situations showing erratic behavior.

The second condition is also problematic for modeling complex systems, since complex systems usually have a very large number of interacting variables. This makes the equations -if such equations can be formulated- not solvable, since the maximum number of variables for generating a closed solution, is usually lower than 5, this is also called "Analytical Intractability".

This does not mean, however, that any system that does not uphold these two conditions cannot be modeled at all. Differential equations can sometimes be exactly solvable, providing a closed

solution³¹, yet in many other cases they are only partially solvable in an approximate way using numerical methods and computer programs, which makes the approximation of the system reliable enough for practical applications.

Nevertheless, we encounter limits to the systems that can be approximately solved. These systems have to meet certain requirements as well, which are lacking in complex systems. There are a number of different conditions that have to be met for a system to be approximately solvable. We will consider only one, which is enough for our purposes³², that of initial and boundary conditions.

4.14.1 Initial and Boundary Conditions for Complex Systems

The real power of differential equations in physics and engineering lies in their ability to predict the future states of a system. Without initial and boundary conditions, these predictions would be impossible, as we wouldn't have a starting point or a defined context for the system.

Differential equations, like those derived from Newton's second law, describe how a system evolves over time or space. However, they don't provide specific information about where or in what state the system begins. Initial and boundary conditions supply this information, defining the specific scenario we're dealing with.

Both initial and boundary conditions are therefore necessarily assumed to be fixed, without invalidating the model. This assumption can be made for simple logic systems, since simple logic systems are homogeneous systems. In simple systems, it's possible to disregard the context; the system's boundary conditions can be considered stable, making the system essentially independent of context.

³¹ A closed solution such as if $2x=4$, then $x=2$.

³² The others can be reviewed in Thurner et al. 2019.

The difficulty arises when looking at complex systems, which are non-homogeneous. The property of homogeneity means that the phenomenon under study is a system that can be taken out of context and separated from the influences it is surrounded by. Setting initial and boundary conditions essentially isolates the system from its surrounding environment, disconnecting it from the rest of the universe.

In such a scenario, nothing other than the initial and boundary conditions externally affects the system's behavior. This ability to isolate systems from their surroundings is a key factor in the historical success of physics, even before the advent of computing technology.

However, for most complex systems, it's challenging to distinctly detach their dynamics from their context. This leads to a situation where numerous external factors, which are not manageable through experimental means, concurrently influence their dynamics (Turner et al. 2019, pp. 3–4). Complex systems are therefore context-dependent; their boundary conditions are constantly changing. Hence these complex systems cannot be modeled in a manner that produces the kind of precise mathematical forecasts required for reliable technological application.

The initial conditions of the system in question must also be assumed to be fixed, without altering the model's behavior. This cannot be assumed for complex systems, since they are, again, context-dependent. Which makes the precise knowledge of their initial conditions practically impossible, they are always chaotic in this regard (Turner et al. 2019, p. 6).

Chaotic behavior in systems, known as deterministic chaos in physics, stems from sensitivity to initial conditions. It occurs in both complex and simple logic systems. Even with known physical laws and a manageable number of variables, predicting behavior in such systems is challenging due to the difficulty in measuring these initial conditions precisely. Examples include the double pendulum, a simple yet unpredictable system, also water molecule behavior in a steam engine, a complex system with chaotic dynamics.

Regardless of the system's complexity, chaos implies that predictions become increasingly inaccurate over time, with this divergence growing exponentially (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 137). This inherent unpredictability in chaotic systems underscores the limitations of mathematical models in accurately forecasting outcomes, especially in the long-term.

Fig. 3 A double pendulum³³: The position of the two spheres cannot be predicted after initial movement due to chaos (the high sensitivity to initial conditions).

It is important to acknowledge that even adequate models can diverge from reality. Although a model may comprehensively describe a system's behavioral patterns, the initial parameters fed into the model's equations are often imprecisely measured. This inaccuracy in measurement can compound when applying a series of differential equations. This phenomenon is why accurately modeling a double pendulum is challenging (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 124).

4.15. Modern approaches to Modeling

Advancements in AI are unlikely to significantly surpass traditional, narrow AI approaches, such as logic-based AI, also called symbolic AI or (GOF-AI)³⁴. Modern AI is defined by its use of optimization frameworks to find extrema in high-dimensional functions, characterized by derivative

³³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Double_pendulum

³⁴ GOF-AI, or "Good Old-Fashioned Artificial Intelligence," refers to the traditional approach to AI that focuses on symbolic processing and rule-based systems, emphasizing logic and structured programming to mimic human reasoning. The term was coined by philosopher John Haugeland in Haugeland 1985.

calculations. This is akin to creating models via loss functions and optimization techniques. Unlike GOF-AI, which requires explicitly designed algorithms, connectionist AI can automatically generate algorithms, making it scalable for large, varied data sets. However, this method is effective only when training samples representatively mirror the variance in target data, limiting its scope.

However, this approach is limited to specific domains where training data accurately reflects the variations in the real-world data it aims to model. Thus, while this utility-based AI offers scalability and the ability to handle large datasets, its effectiveness is confined to areas where such representative training is feasible. Beyond these domains, the approach's utility diminishes, underscoring the narrow focus and limitations of current AI methodologies in replicating broader aspects of human intelligence or dealing with more diverse data scenarios (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 62).

Regardless of how alternative AI is developed, it will inevitably need to mimic a logic system. Essentially, any AI, regardless of its design, must adhere to the principles of physics and logic to predictably function, just like basic mechanical or electronic devices.

4.15.1 Deterministic and Stochastic Modeling for Complex Systems

Computable system models fall into two categories: deterministic and stochastic. Deterministic models include those based on logical systems like propositional, predicate, or modal logic, and encompass expert or rule-based systems. An example is the chess-playing algorithm DeepBlue, which defeated Kasparov in 1996. It employed a deterministic α - β -search algorithm, a method that systematically evaluates and minimizes the possible future moves in the game.

Stochastic models, in contrast to deterministic ones, incorporate elements of randomness and probability. Unlike deterministic models, where outcomes are predictably determined by initial conditions, stochastic models account for the inherent uncertainty and variability in systems.

These models use probability distributions to predict a range of possible outcomes, making them suitable for systems where outcomes are not strictly predetermined. This probabilistic approach allows them to model real-world scenarios more realistically, especially when dealing with uncertain or unpredictable factors. AI models in Natural Language Processing (NLP), like language translation or text generation, use stochastic methods to deal with the unpredictability in language usage.

The mathematical characteristics of deep neural networks (dNNs) adhere to a modified version of Newtonian principles. Specifically, these networks are not constrained by the need for constant or homogeneous interactions among their variables across the entire network. Despite these relaxations, dNNs still need to retain most traditional Newtonian model properties to ensure their computability (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 149).

4.15.2 How Stochastic Modeling Works

To model a process using stochastic methods, we begin by observing the system's behaviors we want to model and translating these observations into numerical data. This data is considered as samples from a distribution, known as a sampling space. Each data type, termed a random variable, encompasses an error, variance, and bias. Errors arise from the limitations in measurement precision. Variance is due to the inherent fluctuations in system behaviors. Bias stems from our observational and data selection methods (Dekking 2005).

We interpret data as distributions to address these random variable characteristics. A distribution is essentially a collection of system measurements, like the height of individuals in a population. This is known as a univariate distribution, which can be graphically represented and often modeled using exponential family distributions such as the Bernoulli or Gaussian distribution. If the data does not fit these models, we term it a non-parametric distribution, which might be

modeled using Bayesian or other non-parametric statistics³⁵ (Dekking 2005; Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 144–145).

Introducing additional variables like weight transforms a univariate into a bivariate distribution, and adding more variables like age, sex, and others creates a multivariate distribution. This multivariate distribution, too complex to visualize on paper, is conceptualized in probability theory as a model for data sets where measurements are seen as random variables. These data sets form a vector space, with each variable's values forming a univariate distribution within that space (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 145).

In certain cases, data distribution can be modeled using parametric distributions. For instance, the Gaussian distribution commonly models human height and weight. Including biological sex, which closely follows a Bernoulli distribution, leads to a mixed Gaussian-Bernoulli distribution (Dekking 2005).

In probability theory, multivariate distributions are often the result of stochastic processes like the Gaussian process. Such processes generate data series that can be modeled as stable multivariate distributions, mathematically representable. By drawing representative samples from a distribution, we can infer properties like mean, median, and skewness. This forms the basis of stochastic methods used in fields ranging from basic statistics to deep Neural Networks (dNNs) (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 145).

However, real-world data usually do not conform to such neatly defined distributions. Ergodic distributions are uncommon, and the distributions typically observed in real-world data are usually non-parametric. They may originate from non-ergodic processes or complex systems, making it challenging to create accurate stochastic models. Models trained on such data will fail with new observations because the real-world distribution can diverge significantly from the

³⁵ Such as the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE).

training distribution, leading to poor performance or even rendering the model ineffective (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 146).

The divergence in models from reality may not be immediately noticeable after model training but tends to increase over time. This means that even if some input data temporarily resembles the training distribution, the overall reliability and trustworthiness of the model in achieving our intentions remain low due to the evolving nature of complex systems (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 146).

4.15.3 Why Modeling Complex Systems Using Logic Systems Will Never be Adequate

There are different reasons why modeling complex systems by logic systems will never be adequate enough to achieve practical application, especially for achieving AGI.

We will first have a look at some of the most important reasons, and then we will show via examples how these problems arise in modern applications whether they are types of deterministic models such as differential equation models or stochastic models such as deep Neural Networks (dNNs).

1. Model Saturation

Model saturation is a term coined by (Larson 2021, p. 155). This term refers to the tendency of stochastic models to plateau in quality, unable to improve further despite the introduction of more training data. This stagnation is attributed to an inherent limitation arising from the use of a logic system to model a complex system. The logical system is intrinsically incapable of matching the performance of the complex system it models, leading to an unbridgeable gap in quality (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 148–149).

2. Vector Space

A *vector space*³⁶ is a mathematical structure formed by a collection of elements called vectors. These vectors can be added together and multiplied by numbers (scalars) (Strang 2021, p. 123). In the context of mathematical models, vectors are used to represent various quantities, depending on the specific model. For example, in physics, vectors might represent forces or velocities; in machine learning, they might represent data points or weights in a neural network (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

A vector space, often a coordinate space, is typically defined over an algebraic field, such as the field of real numbers $\mathbb{R}$. This space comprises sets of n-tuples, which allow for operations like addition and scalar multiplication. A common example is the Euclidean three-dimensional space, represented as $\mathbb{R}^3$, where a vector like (1, 0, 0) is an instance of a 3-tuple in this space.

These vector spaces are crucial for defining variables in mathematical equations that aim to represent real-world systems. However, a significant challenge arises when dealing with complex systems. Unlike simpler systems, complex systems are characterized by variables and interactions that change, often unpredictably. As a result, there is no stable, consistent coordinate space over which these dynamic systems can be effectively modeled (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

The accuracy of a mathematical model heavily depends on how closely the chosen vector space aligns with the actual system it is trying to represent. When the real system deviates from the assumptions inherent in the vector space, the model's validity and accuracy diminish. This deviation can vary from slight to substantial, depending on the extent of change in the actual system (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

³⁶ In physics of dynamical systems it is also called Phase Space. Phase space is a specialized application of the concept of a vector space tailored to the needs of dynamics and mechanics.

This issue is particularly evident in areas like weather forecasting, climate modeling, and epidemiology, where predictions are often only accurate for short periods. Over time, the deviation between the model and the actual system tends to increase, often exponentially. This increasing divergence is due to the evolving nature of complex systems, where new elements may emerge, existing ones may disappear, or unforeseen events may occur, all contributing to a shift away from the original state assumed by the model (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

In essence, the difficulty in modeling complex systems using logic systems stems from their inherently dynamic and unpredictable nature, which often renders static vector spaces and the models built upon them less accurate over time. As the system evolves, so does the gap between the model's assumptions and the system's reality, leading to greater inaccuracies and challenges in effective modeling.

3. *Non-Ergodicity*

Modeling complex systems presents significant challenges, especially when dealing with *non-ergodic* processes. Unlike ergodic processes, which eventually converge to a long-term average and can be analyzed through a single, extensive sample, non-ergodic processes do not offer this consistency. These processes lack predictable, long-term patterns, making it impossible to extract representative samples that are crucial for traditional mathematical modeling.

Neural networks for example are often used to model data generated by various processes. If the data is from an ergodic process, the network can potentially learn general patterns that are representative of the long-term behavior of the process. This is because, in ergodic processes, the time average (observing a single system over a long period) is representative of the ensemble average (observing many systems at a specific time) (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

However, if the data comes from a non-ergodic process, such as complex systems, the neural network will struggle to generalize because the data doesn't settle into a long-term average pattern that's representative of the entire process.

This inconsistency poses a hurdle for modeling using standard mathematical methods, such as differential equations. Some might argue that even complex systems exhibit regularity and can be ergodic. This can be the case for some complex systems, where they might exhibit regular patterns or cycles, like those observed in biological organisms (e.g., respiration, heartbeats, sleep cycles), yet these represent only a fraction of the overall system's behavior. Capturing these partial processes in a mathematical model is not enough because they do not encompass the system's full complexity, variability and the interdependent nature of the system (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

The difficulty lies in the unpredictable nature of these systems. Factors like environmental variations, individual differences, and the intricate interplay of numerous components contribute to the complexity. As a result, while partial modeling of certain aspects or behaviors is possible, developing a comprehensive model that accurately predicts the entire system's behavior will remain a challenge.

4. Process Trace

Modeling non-ergodic processes poses significant challenges, especially in the realm of stochastic modeling. As mentioned earlier, non-ergodic processes are characterized by their lack of a long-term, stable average behavior, which makes the data they generate unsuitable for conventional stochastic sampling. Stochastic models require input data from predictable distributions, like those from the exponential family, or from non-parametric distributions that can be estimated. However, the data from non-ergodic processes do not fit neatly into these categories, making them difficult to model accurately (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

The problem intensifies because samples drawn from non-ergodic process data are inherently unrepresentative of the process as a whole. This unrepresentativeness is due to the absence of a consistent distribution pattern in the process, which defies the basic premise of stochastic

modeling. As a result, any model developed from this data is likely to be flawed or inaccurate (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

This is particularly problematic in applications requiring nuanced understanding and adaptation, such as in creating AGI that can engage meaningfully in human-like conversations and complex environments.

5. Context Dependence

Unlike simple logic systems, complex systems are heavily context-dependent. This means their behavior changes based on the surrounding environment, leading to a dynamic and variable phase space.

Neural networks, for example, always assume that the relationships between inputs and outputs are context-independent (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152). They are trained on datasets assumed to lack contextual nuances. However, this approach is fundamentally limited when applied to complex systems. These systems often exhibit non-ergodic behavior, where long-term average behaviors are not representative of the system as a whole, making it impossible to model them accurately using stochastic methods.

Despite increasing the size of datasets and expanding model parameters, neural networks struggle to accurately model complex systems. The data derived from such systems don't conform to a stable multivariate distribution, making it nearly impossible to draw representative samples for effective training. Consequently, models trained on this data will always be ill-equipped to handle new, unforeseen data from these systems, often responding unpredictably and inadequately due to the mismatch between the training and real-world distributions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

The unpredictability of complex systems is also evident in human behavior within communities and societies. Despite developing various strategies, such as social norms and mutual trust, to increase predictability, humans frequently encounter novel and unexpected situations. These situations, often leading to conflicts, highlight the innate unpredictability in complex system interactions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 149–152).

In summary, while stochastic modeling and neural networks have achieved remarkable successes in certain scientific domains, their ability to accurately model complex, context-dependent systems will always remain limited.

As we have seen, there are profound challenges to mathematically modeling complex systems using principles and methods of logic systems. These challenges are applicable to all types of current as well as future modeling techniques and approaches, since they will all be variants of models based on the paradigm of extended Newtonian mathematics and will therefore be constrained to logic systems. Both stochastic and deterministic models are essentially based on logic systems. This is primarily because they can be executed on Turing machines, which are themselves logic system operators.

We can distinguish between artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning. Artificial intelligence is the field of research which involves incorporating human knowledge and reasoning processes into AI systems, it also refers to the development of computer-based intelligence, encompassing a period of the last 70 years (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, p. 11). Machine learning, a subfield of AI, relies on supplying vast volumes of data to an algorithm, which then autonomously learns from this data. Deep learning, a specific branch within machine learning, draws its inspiration from the architecture and functioning of the human brain (such as dNNs) (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, p. 4).

Fig. 4 AI Eco-System

Since we already examined deterministic approaches earlier, such as differential equation models, we will turn to some examples of modern stochastic approaches that try to model complex systems and show why they will fail to come even close to modeling complex systems³⁷. For better readability will categorize modern stochastic models in Machine Learning into types and techniques as follows:

- Types
 - Supervised learning
 - Unsupervised Learning
 - Reinforcement Learning
- Techniques
 - Stochastic Differential Equation Models
 - Deep Neural Networks
 - Feed Forward Neural Networks
 - Convolutional Neural Networks
 - Recurrent Neural Networks
 - Generative Adversarial Networks
 - Attention-based Neural Networks

³⁷ For an extensive analysis see Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 160–178.

4.15.4 Types of Machine Learning

4.15.4.1 Supervised Learning

Supervised learning is a prevalent type of machine learning (ML) and involves predicting a target value, such as a class or label, based on input features. This is akin to recognizing a motorbike by its features and categorizing it accordingly. In supervised learning, input data, structured in data frames, is labeled with corresponding classes. The algorithm identifies patterns in these features to accurately predict outcomes (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, 56,63).

However, raw data isn't immediately suitable for ML training. It requires selecting relevant features that effectively distinguish between classes, such as focusing on age and sex for a specific dataset, while discarding less useful ones like names and ticket numbers (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, 56,63).

Supervised learning involves creating a function from labeled training data, which includes examples and their corresponding target values. The trained model is then tested with unseen data to evaluate its performance, predicting the class an observation belongs to based on its features (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, 56,63).

Besides training data, there's also test data for evaluating the model and validation data for tuning the model during training. The choice of the right learning approach, whether for classification or regression tasks, is crucial in developing successful ML solutions. Each ML type is suited to specific tasks and data types, and supervised learning is particularly useful for categorization and prediction tasks (Fergus and Chalmers 2022, 56,63).

But for supervised learning to perform its desired outcomes there are several assumptions that must be satisfied³⁸, some of these include:

- There is a clearly defined problem to solve
- There is adequate data
- It makes sense to model the problem
- You can manage the lifecycle of the model (it is very rarely a success on the first attempt) and will require continuous improvement over time
- You have the computational capacity to train and host the model
- You have the relevant domain expertise to validate the model

Unfortunately, complex systems almost always contradict most of these assumptions. For example, complex systems, such as humans or vertebrates do not have a clearly defined problem, they are adaptable to a range of different problems in complex environments and are creative in their way of reaching solutions to these problems. Also, for modeling complex systems, it is challenging to have enough adequate data, since the data assumes the system to be ergodic, context-independent and fitting a certain non-parametric distribution. Of course, since supervised learning continuously needs improvement through human input over time, it contradicts the basic premise of AGI being an autonomous agent.

4.15.4.2 Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning is a machine learning approach focused on pattern or sequence identification without using pre-labeled training data (Geoffrey E. Hinton and T. Sejnowski 2018). Instead of the typical input-output tuples, it relies solely on a data matrix with dimensions corresponding to the number of observations and the number of dimensions. Without an outcome variable, there's no direct "teacher" or "trainer"; the process involves exploring a multi-

³⁸ For these Assumptions see Fergus and Chalmers 2022, pp. 64–65.

dimensional distribution of data to uncover inherent characteristics of the probability density without a specific outcome (Ghahramani 2004).

These methods can discern patterns and are useful for data exploration, pattern identification, and detecting anomalies or outliers. However, they require human interpretation and application as well as supervised learning in downstream tasks³⁹ (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 176–177).

Unsupervised sequence learning allows systems to generate output sequences from input data based on the learned probability density (Geoffrey E. Hinton and T. Sejnowski 2018). The output is a pattern derived from the input, often resembling a subset of sequences from the training set. This capability is exemplified in applications like sentence completion suggestions in email writing. However, these models also face limitations in complex system modeling because, as we have seen, complex systems do not conform to any sort of multivariate distributions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 177).

4.15.4.3 Reinforcement Learning

In reinforcement learning, a machine interacts with its environment by executing actions ($a_1, a_2, \dots$). These actions alter the environment's state, leading to the machine obtaining scalar rewards or incurring punishments ($r_1, r_2, \dots$). The machine's objective is to modify its actions to maximize the rewards it accumulates (or to minimize punishments) throughout its operational life (Ghahramani 2004).

Reinforcement learning is primarily used in gaming, as seen in games like Go. Optimized through numerous games, this approach excels in settings where outcomes are quantifiable by the machine, like in specific games or tasks. However, it faces limitations in complex systems, where dNNs succeeded only in simplified settings without human interaction elements. This approach is effective in predictable, closed-world environments but struggles with the open, complex nature

³⁹ downstream tasks are specific, often practical applications for which a pre-trained machine learning model is further refined and utilized, allowing it to apply its general learning to particular problems or scenarios.

of real-world settings, failing to capture the nuances of human behaviors and interactions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 173–175).

Consequently, reinforcement learning is limited in its application to complex systems and real-life scenarios, where the dynamic and unpredictable nature of events cannot be adequately addressed by a system reliant on clear, consistent, and automatic scoring.

4.15.5 Techniques of Machine Learning

4.15.5.1 Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE) Models

Differential equations are a powerful tool in modeling a variety of processes, including those that evolve over time. They can even be adapted to incorporate stochastic effects. This extension allows differential equations to represent not just the deterministic aspects of a process, but also its random elements, providing a more comprehensive model of certain physical phenomena.

However, when it comes to modeling complex systems, even these stochastically modified differential equations encounter significant limitations. The reason for this is the dual set of assumptions that must be met for both differential equations and stochastic process models to be effective. As previously explained, differential equations typically assume a certain level of continuity and predictability in the processes they model, while stochastic models require specific statistical properties related to randomness and distribution (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 164–165).

Complex systems, characterized by their intricate, interconnected components and often unpredictable behavior, do not neatly conform to these assumptions. The inherent complexity of these systems means that the behavior of their constituent parts and their interactions cannot be captured accurately by the structured framework of differential equations, even when extended to include stochastic elements. Moreover, the randomness inherent in complex systems often

does not align with the structured nature of stochastic processes as typically modeled (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 164).

In essence, the failure of both sets of assumptions—those underpinning differential equations and those crucial for stochastic models—renders these approaches inadequate for fully capturing the dynamics of complex systems. The unpredictable, non-linear, and chaotic nature of these systems poses a significant challenge that goes beyond the capabilities of traditional mathematical modeling techniques, including differential equations, even when they are enhanced with stochastic components.

4.15.5.2 (deep) Neural Networks (dNNs)

Recent years have seen a surge of interest in a specific subclass of stochastic models known as *deep Neural Networks* (dNNs), often associated with *deep learning* or *self-learning*. These models have garnered considerable attention due to their unique capabilities in handling complex modeling tasks (Noman 2020).

Fig.5 Schematic of a Deep Neural Network⁴⁰

Deep Neural Networks (dNNs) stand out in the modeling field for their adept handling of non-parametric multivariate distributions, even in complex scenarios with numerous input dimensions, such as language translation using neural networks. This capability represents a substantial advancement in the construction of mathematical models, differing fundamentally from traditional methods that depend on explicit equation writing. Instead, dNNs rely on implicit model construction, utilizing optimization algorithms—a technique that has seen remarkable progress in recent AI research due to the availability of vast digital data and significant computational power (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 165; Noman 2020).

These advancements have led to notable successes across various AI domains, highlighting the importance of these developments in the realm of mathematical modeling. The methodology employed by dNNs, and machine learning techniques in general, differs markedly from classical statistical models, which are typically created through a methodical mathematical process of data

⁴⁰ https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Neural_network.png

observation and equation formulation (Noman 2020). In contrast, dNNs automatically generate models through optimization algorithms. Human involvement in these models is mainly focused on setting hyperparameters, defining network architecture, determining optimization goals, and selecting training material. This material, which includes the functionals the algorithm learns, shifts the emphasis from traditional equation modeling to a process where the algorithm is guided to learn from the data provided. This approach underlines a significant shift in model creation, moving away from explicit mathematical design to leveraging algorithmic learning capabilities (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 165).

4.15.5.3 The Myth of “Self-learning”

Contrary to popular belief, AI systems do not learn in the same manner as animals and humans. Similar to what we have seen when investigating the Chinese Room Argument (CRA) as well as the Eliza Effect, the process commonly referred to as “learning” in AI, especially in neural network training, diverges fundamentally from the learning observed in vertebrates. AI systems perform computations (syntax manipulation) using optimization algorithms to create operators that minimize loss or optimize reward, which is markedly different from the learning and adaptation seen in biological organisms. The term “learning” in AI context does not encompass the continuous and adaptive extension into new areas, as is characteristic of human or animal learning (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 167).

In fact, the AI’s learning process, often termed “training,” does not align with the true sense of learning as understood in the context of humans or animals. Machines process algorithms derived from optimization theory, and any deviation from the expected input data can and will lead to incorrect predictions.

Moreover, the concept of “self-learning” in AI is misleading. It suggests an autonomous acquisition of knowledge akin to human learning, but in reality, human intervention is crucial in preparing and transforming training data, as well as in scheduling re-training. Machines merely execute computations as programmed, without independent action or decision-making.

The complexity of biological systems, especially the nervous system, far exceeds that of any AI model or any dNN even with billions of parameters. A typical neuron in a nervous system, for instance, integrates signals through millions of molecules and connects to other neurons in various ways, influenced by numerous factors. This complexity, combined with the dynamic nature of living cells, positions biological systems as inherently complex while any AI model is, at its core, a computational logic system designed to approximate complex systems but not replicate them fully (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 168–169).

4.15.5.4 Data Greed of dNNs

Deep Neural Networks (dNNs) require vast amounts of data for effective training, a requirement that often hampers their performance due to various limitations. One such limitation is the concept known as the “curse of dimensionality”. In machine learning, especially relevant to Deep Neural Networks (dNNs), it becomes a major issue when dealing with high-dimensional input spaces, such as those in machine translation or image and shape classification (Nan Wu et al. 2022).

This term refers to the challenges that arise when the number of features or variables in the model (the dimensionality) is very high. In high-dimensional spaces, the data becomes sparse, meaning the data points are spread out, mostly closer to the boundary of the sample space rather than clustered together. This sparsity makes it difficult for dNNs to discern patterns in the data, which is crucial for learning and making accurate predictions (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 169–170).

As a result, despite the need for handling hundreds of dimensions in many applications, the available data remains too sparse to train dNNs effectively, severely limiting their predictive capabilities. When data is sparse and a model is trained on a limited dataset, it becomes problematic for the model to classify or predict accurately. The model is likely to fail when it encounters new data that is significantly different from what it was trained on, simply because it has not learned from enough varied examples to handle new, unforeseen situations effectively (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 170).

Complex systems such as humans and animals, on the other hand, are adept at dealing with novel situations, often using creative thinking to navigate unfamiliar scenarios. This flexibility and ability to deal with novel data is something that statistical models lack.

4.15.5.5 Feed Forward Neural Networks

Deep feedforward networks, also known as feedforward neural networks or multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), are fundamental models in deep learning. Their primary function is to approximate some function f^* , like mapping an input x to a category y in classification tasks. These networks are termed “feedforward” because the data flows from the input x through intermediate computations to the output y , without any feedback loops. When these networks incorporate feedback connections, they evolve into recurrent neural networks, used extensively in natural language processing (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 164–165).

Feedforward networks are critically important in the field of machine learning, underpinning many commercial applications such as convolutional networks for object recognition in photos. They are not only essential in practical applications but also serve as a conceptual bridge to more complex models like recurrent neural networks (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 164–165).

The structure of feedforward neural networks is based on composing multiple functions, creating a directed acyclic graph that outlines how these functions are combined. For instance, a network might consist of functions $f(1)$, $f(2)$, and $f(3)$ arranged in a chain, forming $f(x) = f(3)(f(2)(f(1)(x)))$. This chain-like structure, where the length of the chain determines the network's depth, is common in neural networks. The depth of these models is the reason the term “deep learning” was coined. The final layer in such a network is the output layer, which is trained to approximate $f^*(x)$ (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 164–165).

Training data for these networks provides examples of $f^*(x)$, each consisting of an input x and a corresponding label y , indicating the desired output. While the output layer's function is explicitly

defined by the training data, the roles of the other layers, known as hidden layers, are not. The hidden layers must be configured by the learning algorithm to optimally approximate f^* , but how they do this is not specified by the training data. This setup necessitates the algorithm to determine the best use of these hidden layers to effectively approximate the desired function (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 164–165).

A problem with Feed-Forward Neural Networks, however, is that it assumes “*data independence*”. For the convergence of neural network (NN) models to the correct solution they have to assume that the data are independent and identically distributed (iid) (Charniak 2019, p. 24). A classic example illustrating this principle is cosmic ray measurements, where rays arrive in a random yet consistent manner (Charniak 2019, p. 24). However, real-world data, especially complex systems, rarely conform to this iid assumption. This deviation from iid can start as early as the second training example, a situation often encountered in deep reinforcement learning (deep RL) (Charniak 2019, p. 24). Consequently, networks in deep RL frequently experience instability, manifesting as a failure to converge to the correct or any solution. Even inputting data in a non-random order in relatively minor examples can lead to significantly adverse outcomes, underscoring the challenges posed by non-iid data such as complex systems in neural network training and performance.

4.15.5.6 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional networks, or Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), are a type of neural network specifically designed for processing data with a grid-like structure, such as time-series data (viewed as a 1-D grid) and image data (considered as a 2-D grid of pixels). These networks have gained substantial success in practical applications, particularly due to their use of convolution, a special linear operation, instead of general matrix multiplication in at least one layer (Charniak 2019, p. 51; Goodfellow et al. 2017, p. 326).

Convolutional neural networks, which have shown particular effectiveness in computer vision tasks. However, this approach doesn't mirror human visual perception, which relies more on

relative differences in light intensity rather than absolute values, and primarily focuses on local variations (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 326–327).

This understanding leads to the realization that in scene recognition, what matters are the local differences in light intensity. For instance, a light patch on wallpaper across a room from a lightbulb may reflect fewer photons than a darker patch near the bulb, yet it appears lighter due to these local intensity differences. CNNs capitalize on this principle of local differences, making them adept at interpreting and processing visual data in a way that's more aligned with human perception (Goodfellow et al. 2017, pp. 326–327).

Convolutional networks, adept at processing data with grid-like topologies, have found significant success in handling two-dimensional image data. However, their ability to model complex systems like the human visual system will remain limited. The human visual system integrates with other senses, including hearing, and is influenced by factors such as moods and thoughts, aspects that convolutional networks, which are predominantly visual, do not incorporate (Goodfellow et al. 2017, p. 361).

Beyond mere object recognition, the human visual system comprehends entire scenes, discerning multiple objects, their interrelations, and processing rich three-dimensional geometric information crucial for physical interaction with complex environments. While convolutional networks have begun to be applied to some of these more complex visual tasks, these efforts are still in the early stages. Additionally, even relatively simple brain regions, like the visual cortex area V1, are influenced by feedback from higher brain levels, a phenomenon that has been explored in neural network models but without any improvements so far (Goodfellow et al. 2017, p. 361).

Convolutional networks are also specifically suited for variably sized inputs that contain different amounts of similar observations, like varying lengths of time series or spatial observations. They are less effective when the variability in input size is due to the inclusion of different types of observations. For instance, in processing simple college applications where features might include grades and optional standardized test scores, convolutional networks would struggle. Applying

the same convolutional weights to disparate types of data, such as grades and test scores, isn't effective because these data categories fundamentally differ in nature and relevance (Goodfellow et al. 2017, p. 354).

In summary, while convolutional networks excel in processing grid-structured data, particularly in image recognition, they fall short in adequately modeling even parts of complex systems like the human visual system, which involves multi-sensory integration, higher-dimensional scene understanding, and feedback mechanisms. Their design is also not conducive to handling inputs comprising varied types of data, limiting their applicability in scenarios requiring nuanced interpretation of diverse information categories, which are always existent in complex environments.

4.15.5.7 Deep recurrent Neural Network (rNN) models

Deep recurrent neural networks (drNNs) are a type of neural network designed to primarily model sequence processing such as text, audio and video (Noman 2020). These networks, often referred to as sequence-to-sequence dNNs, excel in tasks like translating one sequence of words into another. A common approach within these networks involves Long-Term Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models and their various extensions, which have been widely applied in practical AI applications, including neural network-based translation (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 171–172).

The success of rNNs in handling numerical time-series data can be attributed to several factors⁴¹:

1. The data generally aligns, albeit approximately, with the assumptions required for stochastic process modeling, of which dNNs and rNNs are a subset.
2. These datasets are often large and repetitive, providing ample historical data for training.
3. The data tend to have low dimensionality and variance.

⁴¹ See Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 171–172.

4. dNN architectures are adept at modeling temporal pattern overlays, such as those seen in traffic patterns with daily and weekly cycles.

However, when it comes to modeling the behavior of complex systems, several challenges arise:

- i. Complex systems exhibit erratic, rather than repetitive, behavior.
- ii. They do not meet the central assumptions needed for temporal process models, which are also critical for the success of rNNs in such modeling tasks.
- iii. They involve extremely high dimensionality.
- iv. They do not offer a multivariate distribution from which adequate samples can be drawn, as novel behavior can emerge at any stage, resulting in input-output pairs derived from a constantly shifting and elusive distribution.

This shows that while rNNs show proficiency in managing numerical time-series data due to their alignment with specific data characteristics and modeling capabilities, they will struggle significantly in the realm of complex systems due to their inherent limitations.

4.15.5.7 Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) models

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are a type of deep neural network or deep generative models based on game theory, they consist of two interconnected networks: a generative network that creates new data samples, and a discriminative network that classifies these samples (Noman 2020). GANs have proven effective in image processing tasks, using pre-trained discriminative networks on accurately tagged images.

However, their application is limited in complex systems modeling, such as generating meaningful human activities, due to challenges in training the discriminative network and the lack of diverse, context-rich training data (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 172–173). Consequently, while GANs show promise in specific areas, their ability to handle broader, more complex tasks is very much constrained.

4.15.5.7.1 Evolutionary GANs

More recently, evolutionary GANs have been proposed to address some of the limitations inherent in traditional GANs, such as the fixed generator objective function. These models employ a population of generators, each with a different adversarial training objective, to perform mutation operations. This approach enhances the computational properties of GANs and yields more diverse outputs. However, it does not solve the fundamental challenges that all dNNs face in modeling complex systems, as it still relies on the same foundational principles of GAN architecture (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, pp. 172–173).

4.15.5.8 Attention-Based Neural Networks

Finally, the attention mechanism is a concept in artificial intelligence that has been around for over 30 years, which underwent a significant revolution with the introduction of the Transformer model in 2017 (Vaswani et al. 2017). This model demonstrated the pivotal role of attention in achieving remarkable improvements in power consumption, accuracy, and processing speed, setting a new standard in the field.

Previously, attention mechanisms were typically used in conjunction with other models like CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) and RNNs (Recurrent Neural Networks). However, the Transformer model showed that attention mechanisms alone could produce high-quality outputs. This was a departure from earlier approaches, emphasizing the standalone efficacy of attention-based models (Chen 2022).

The principle of attention in AI is inspired by the human cognitive process, focusing on the relative importance of different elements in a given context. For instance, in a visual scene, certain objects are more critical than others, similar to how nouns in a sentence often carry more weight than adjectives. The attention mechanism in AI models mimics this by assigning varying weights to

different parts of the input data, enhancing the model's ability to focus on the most relevant information (Chen 2022).

The implementation of attention can range from simple vector dot product calculations to more complex structures like those found in the Transformer model. Regardless of the complexity, the underlying concept remains the same. The attention mechanism distributes importance across various elements, enabling the model to concentrate on the most pertinent information. The flexibility of this mechanism is crucial, especially when dealing with inputs that contain limited characteristics from the original data (Chen 2022). Models like Transformers have excelled in this aspect, offering a more adaptable and effective approach to handling attention, which has been instrumental in their success and widespread adoption in tasks like language translation, text generation, and understanding context in large datasets such as ChatGPT⁴².

However, attention models do have limitations, particularly regarding their interpretability and performance, which highlight their inadequacy in modeling complex systems and environments. The interpretability of these models is highly contested; while some researchers propose that the weight distribution in attention mechanisms indicates the model's understanding of data importance, we argue that this is a superficial interpretation. The complexities and numerous components in the model's computation make it difficult to control variables or fully grasp the reasoning behind the model's decisions (Chen 2022). The lack of standardized metrics for interpretability further undermines the reliability of these models in providing clear, understandable insights into their processing.

Moreover, the effectiveness of attention models is heavily dependent on the size of the dataset (Chen 2022). While they perform well with large-scale pre-training on extensive datasets, their efficacy significantly decreases with smaller datasets. This inconsistency in performance highlights a critical shortcoming, as real-world applications often involve varied and limited data. In contrast to human learning, which requires comparatively much less data and benefits from some sort of

⁴² GPT stands for "Generative Pre-trained Transformer."

optimized initial parameters, attention models start from scratch and demand an immense amount of data for effective learning (Chen 2022). This vast data requirement underscores the models' inability to efficiently process and learn from limited information, a crucial aspect of dealing with complex systems.

Therefore, despite the advancements in attention models and transformers, their current form and functionality render them unsuitable for accurately and efficiently modeling complex systems, particularly in scenarios with constrained or diverse data environments. The challenges in interpretability and the dependency on large datasets are significant barriers that prevent these models from adequately adapting to the intricacies of complex systems.

5. Conclusion

5.1 What we would need to achieve AGI

As we have seen in the previous chapter, we cannot adequately model complex systems. We cannot even mathematically explain the most simplest of complex systems such as turbulence⁴³ of water, let alone predict or model it. If we cannot model even the simplest of complex systems, it is unimaginable to think that we can model complex complex systems such as human intelligence or brains of vertebrates.

The question now becomes, how could we then, assuming it is ontologically possible⁴⁴, achieve AGI?

We would firstly need to be able to move beyond the paradigm of extended Newtonian Mathematics. As long as our mathematical methods are limited to forms of Newtonian mathematics and we rely on algorithms from this mathematical domain that are executable on universal Turing machines, it seems highly unlikely that we will succeed in mathematically modeling and eventually engineering a system complex enough to mimic human intelligence.

We would need a fundamental revolution in mathematics, a revolution that surpasses the revolution brought to us by the invention of calculus by Newton and Leibnitz. A revolution of this sort, however, does not seem to be anywhere in sight. In fact, many leaders in the field have deemed such a revolution as impossible, such as Richard Feynman and Werner Heisenberg (Feynman 1970; Marshak and Davis 2005).

⁴³ Turbulence refers to the complex and chaotic state of fluid flow, which is characterized by irregular, unpredictable motion. Turbulence, according to Richard Feynman, is “the most important unsolved problem of classical physics” Feynman 1970.

⁴⁴ Meaning there are no ontological restrictions, such as substance dualism or vitalism being true.

Furthermore, even if we consider the possibility of a non-human (extraterrestrial) form of intelligence capable of handling environments generated by complex systems (similar to humans and animals), we would not be able to replicate such intelligence. This is because any emulation of this kind would inherently require a level of complexity beyond our current capabilities (Landgrebe and Smith 2022, p. 190).

Additionally, we would need a similar revolution in computation, that would allow us to move beyond the Church-Turing paradigm on computability. We would need computers that are not limited to the execution of algorithms of the extended Newtonian paradigm, but computers that would allow the execution of this new mathematical paradigm, that hypothetically, would allow us to model complex systems. These objectives present themselves as an immensely daunting, if not virtually insurmountable challenge for the foreseeable future.

5.2 Implications of This Discussion

The arguments presented in this thesis should have numerous implications on different sectors. From a financial as well as an academic perspective, a huge amount of money is going to the funding of projects on AGI research and development. If AGI is in principle not achievable, this funding should be redirected to projects that are achievable or can still be enhanced such as projects in narrow AI. Unfortunately, this implication seems to be one of the major reasons why there exists a range of hostility towards those who spread doubt about the AGI mission.

John Searle points this out accurately when he writes:

Many people have a professional commitment to Strong AI. To put the point bluntly, in many cases their careers and the funding of their research projects depend on the continued belief that they are 'creating minds' (one Strong AI worker actually assured me that he was 'creating minds'). For such people it is psychologically impossible to accept that the project of Strong AI is misconceived in principle. They would like to believe that the failure of Strong AI is due to some temporary limitation of the technology; that if only we had faster computer chips or more complex parallel distributed processing systems, we would be able to overcome the argument (Searle 2023).

From a sociological point of view, these conclusions should decrease the widespread hype but also some of the fear surrounding the advancements in the field of AI. If AGI is not achievable, theories about the singularity and machine world domination remain a matter of science fiction rather than reality. This is not to neglect the ethical considerations about AI and the range of misuses and danger of AI, but rather to put these considerations into their realistic frame, the fear of AI should not be a fear of an existential scale but of malice use and data protection.

Finally, many AGI proponents might not be aware of the challenges of achieving AGI, simply due to the nature of the contemporary nature of academia. This is due to the increased polarization of the sciences, where students of a specific science, are not only insulated to their own field, but they are insulated to a certain paradigm of their science.

This issue has been noticed by Thomas Kuhn in his famous work “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions”, where he talks about the “nature of educational initiation” (Kuhn 2015, p. 165). Unlike the social sciences and philosophy, where the students get to read some of the primary works of the earlier scholars, students of the natural sciences and engineering usually never do so. These students mainly rely on textbooks that are written to briefly supply the most up-to-date information to students, inside the paradigm that is already established (Kuhn 2015, 80,165).

Therefore, it is not difficult to see why most computer scientists are philosophically illiterate, not having rigorously engaged in fundamental questions on computation and the nature of intelligence. This reflects the problem of extreme specialization, where a narrow focus on technical aspects leads to a lack of broader philosophical understanding. An interdisciplinary approach, integrating philosophy, mathematics, and computer science, is crucial to comprehensively explore and address the profound questions of artificial intelligence and computational theory.

6. References

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Appendix A

a:

1. Constant Function: This is a simple function that always returns the same value, regardless of the input. For example, a constant function might always return the number 3, no matter what input it receives.

2. Successor Function: The successor function is a basic arithmetic function that takes a number as input and returns the next number. For instance, if you input 2, the successor function returns 3.

3. It's a way of incrementally increasing a value by one and is fundamental in the construction of natural numbers in mathematical logic.

3. Identity Function: An identity function is a function that returns its input unchanged. If you input 'x' into an identity function, it will output 'x'. It's called 'identity' because the output is identical to the input.

4. Composition Operator: In mathematics, the composition of functions is an operation that takes two functions and forms a new function. If you have two functions, say f and g , the composition (denoted as $f \circ g$) means you first apply g to an input and then apply f to the result of g . It's a way of combining functions to create more complex functions.

5. Primitive Recursion: This is a concept used to define a certain class of functions that are computable. A function is defined using primitive recursion if it can be constructed from basic functions (like constant, successor, and identity functions) using specific operations, including the composition of functions and a form of recursion that builds complex functions from simpler ones in a very controlled manner.